

Correlation between Availability ... (Shuaibu, 2023) DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10071995>

Correlation between Availability of Educational Resources and Academic Performance in Biology among Secondary School Students in Adamawa State

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Abstract

The study investigated the relationship between educational resources and biology students' academic performance in Adamawa state, Nigeria. The study adopted a correlational design. The target population of the study comprised 12,143 teachers and 731 principals of senior secondary schools in the five-education zone of Adamawa state. A sample of 221 teachers was used. The instruments used for data collection was Educational Resources Questionnaire tagged (ERQ). Mean and standard deviation were used to analyzed the data. The findings of the study are: availability of instructional aids is a significant predictor of senior secondary school Biology students' academic achievement, $F_{(1, 220)} = 14.368$, $p < 0.05$ school facilities is a significant predictor of senior secondary school students' academic achievement, $F_{(1, 220)} = 16.057$, $p < 0.05$ and adequacy of funding is a significant predictor of senior secondary school students' academic achievement, $F_{(1, 220)} = 26.145$, $p < 0.05$. It is recommended among others that government through the post primary school management board should make instructional aids available to schools to enable teachers teach effectively.

Keywords: Educational resource, Students' academic performance, Biology

Introduction

Education is the process of emancipation, civilization and development, and also a key that unlocks the development of personal and national potentials/national development (Ekokotu & Okeh, 2012). For this reason, the National Policy on Education (FRN, 2014) described education as an instrument par excellence for effective national development. Development ideas, scientific advancement, vocational and technological breakthrough, economic development are made possible by the educational theories and practices (Garuba, Agweda & Abumere, 2012). According to Tunde, Akintoye, and Adeyemo (2011), science education is crucial to the development of any country, which is why every country needs to take it seriously in all educational institutions. Biology, chemistry, and physics are the three subjects that make up science education; over the past year, enrollment in these subjects in our schools has been low, according to Aina (2012).

Biology is the study of animals and plants, and it helps develop the scientific literacy necessary for a nation to grow and develop. Ezeh (2006) asserts that a nation's capacity for scientific literacy will have a significant influence on how far it can advance. Scientific literacy is growing in popularity daily as a result of science and technology's global expansion and advancement. Biology explains human anatomy and physiology, health issues, and how to comprehend, deal with, and manage the microbes that surround us. Biology is a requirement for many tertiary institutions' science and science-related courses. If educational resources are sufficiently provided and used, Biology teaching and learning will be improved. The human and material resources found in schools may be regarded as educational resources.

The availability of qualified teachers, access to infrastructural facilities, the quality of teaching aids, the implementation of curricula, and funding are just a few examples of the many factors that Sharka (2008) defines as educational resources. Educational resources can be either human, material, or financial resources. This study looked into how funding, school resources, and teaching resources related to academic achievement among biology students. A useful educational tool that supports the educational objectives of secondary schools is instructional aid at the secondary school level. Secondary institutions A teacher will use instructional aides to help students understand and appreciate the lesson's goals by conveying to them the key information in a lesson. For effective teaching to occur and for learners' learning outcomes to change, the use of instructional materials is a requirement (Jimoh, 2009). Ikerionwu (2000) defined instructional aids in secondary schools as things or tools that help the teacher make learning relevant to the student. They are tools for helping people transfer information to one another (Adeoye, 2012). In other words, instructional materials increase the effectiveness of secondary education by enhancing the standard of both teaching and learning. It provides a variety of learning opportunities that can be used singly or in combination to meet various teaching and learning needs and to inspire students to become skilled technicians with a never-

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ending passion for learning. According to Okobia (2011), the benefits of using instructional materials in the classroom include, among other things, making the subject matter more realistic, explaining challenging concepts, having the learner experience what they are learning, igniting the learners' imaginations, avoiding misconceptions, and making learning interesting.

The goal of instructional materials is to increase the effectiveness of education by raising the standard of both teaching and learning. As a result, the use of instructional aids is dependent upon their accessibility in the classroom. Resources for secondary school education that are required for a high-quality secondary education outcome include infrastructure facilities as well.

Jimoh (2009) claims that by meeting the physical and emotional needs of the faculty and students at the school, secondary school infrastructure facilities play a crucial role in the realization of the goals and objectives of secondary education. The physical resources made available to secondary school staff and students to maximize their productivity in the teaching and learning process are known as infrastructural facilities.

The realization that the transfer of knowledge does not only take place in the four walls of the classroom from the teacher to the students but rather than learning takes place through discovery, exploration, interaction with the internal and external environment has necessitated the creative and innovative development of teaching and learning facilities that reflect these changes. Secondary schools exist to serve socio-economic and political needs of the ever-changing society; consequently, they are in constant interaction with their external environment. They receive inputs from the external environment in the form of human and material resources, process them and empty same into the society as finished products and services. The quality of the products bears a direct relationship with the quality of the facilities deployed in the process of the production.

Secondary school funding stands out as the mother of secondary education resources, because the availability of other secondary education resources is directly related to the level of secondary school funding. The financing of secondary education as an aspect of public finance embraces all aspects of funding of secondary schools, including the sources of funding and how the money earmarked for secondary education is spent especially for the purchase of goods and the services of human and materials. Thus, the financing of secondary education is a vital area of Economics of Education. The importance of adequate financing of secondary education cannot be over-stressed. Taggert (2003) argued that no organization could carry out its functions effectively without adequate financial resources at its disposal. Money is needed to pay staff, maintain the plant and keep the services going. This argument supported earlier findings that finance is of vital importance to education and economic growth (Omotade, 2004). Base on this background it is obvious that to sustain progress in the secondary school agenda and to attain the desired secondary education product, we need more efficiency in the use of human and material resources in education and sustainable policies to accelerate educational growth. Thus, this study investigated the relationship between educational resources and secondary schools Biology students' academic performance in Adamawa State.

The Federal Republic of Nigeria's 2014 National Policy on secondary education emphasizes the importance of equipping students with fundamental scientific knowledge, practical skills, and applied abilities to facilitate their further education. Achieving this goal hinges on the availability of sufficient educational resources, which are the most visible aspects of government educational provision and are regularly observed by stakeholders. Insufficient human and material resources can hinder the attainment of educational objectives, potentially resulting in inadequately prepared secondary school graduates who lack the necessary technical and applied skills for everyday life, rendering them less useful to society. Moreover, these graduates may struggle to meet the requirements of higher education, leading to dropouts or dismissals due to underperformance. These issues may stem from inadequate instructional methods, a lack of appropriate teaching aids for comprehensive understanding, and the improper implementation of the curriculum at the secondary school level.

Educational resources are pivotal to the teaching and learning process and directly impact students' academic performance. Consequently, there is a pressing need to ensure the provision of adequate educational resources in senior secondary schools. These schools are grappling with a multitude of problems, including inadequate resource allocation due to poor planning. Furthermore, there is a growing concern regarding the declining academic performance of students, particularly in English language and mathematics, in Adamawa state, especially in its rural and semi-rural areas. This decline is evident through poor performance in the West African Senior School Certificate Examination (WASSCE). In light of these challenges, this research seeks to investigate whether the availability of educational resources serves as a predictor of students' academic performance in Adamawa state.

Purpose of the Study

The study investigated the relationship between availability of educational resources and academic performance in Biology among secondary schools' students in Adamawa State. Specifically, the study determined:

1. The relationship between availability of instructional aids and Biology students' academic achievement in Adamawa state.

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2. The relationship between availability of school facilities and Biology students’ academic achievement in Adamawa state.
3. The relationship between adequacy of funding in senior secondary schools and Biology students’ academic achievement in Adamawa state.

Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study

1. What is the level of availability of instructional aids in senior secondary schools in Adamawa state?
2. What is the level of availability of school facilities in senior secondary schools in Adamawa state?
3. What is the level of adequacy of funding in senior secondary schools in Adamawa state?

Hypotheses

The following null hypothesis were formulated and tested at 0.05 level of significance.

1. **H₀₁**: There is no significant relationship between availability of instructional aids and Biology students’ academic achievement in senior secondary schools in Adamawa state.
2. **H₀₂**: There is no significant relationship between availability of school facilities and Biology students’ academic achievement in senior secondary schools in Adamawa state.
3. **H₀₃**: There is no significant relationship between adequacy of funding and students’ academic performance in senior secondary schools in Adamawa state.

Methodology

The study employed a correlational design. The target population of the study comprised 12,143 teachers and 731 principals of senior secondary schools in the five-education zone of Adamawa state. A sample of 221 teachers was used. The instruments used for data collection was Educational Resources Questionnaire tagged (ERQ). It is a 26 – items questionnaire divided into three sections. The ERQ is based on five-point rating scale of vary high level (VHL), high level (HL), moderate level (MD), low level (LL) and very low level (VLL). Mean and standard deviation were used to analyzed the data.

Results

Research Question 1

What is the level of availability of instructional aids in senior secondary schools in Adamawa state?

Table 1: Mean and Standard Deviation of Level of availability of Instructional Aids in Senior Secondary Schools in Adamawa State

S/N	ITEM	n = 221	Mean	S. D
1	How available is Dictionary for teaching purpose		4.10	1.47
2	How available are Charts used for teaching		4.36	1.33
3	How available are Models for teaching		3.45	1.67
4	How available are Maps of the World for promoting learning and interest		3.10	1.63
5	How available are Textbooks in the library for student’s usage		3.34	1.64
6	How available are classroom Blackboards for teaching		3.16	1.61
7	How available are Simulation games that enhances learning		3.45	1.63
8	How available are Real objects for teaching purpose?		2.63	1.49
9	How available are Films and videos for audio- visual instructional approach of teaching?		3.98	1.47
10	How available are computers in the school for ICT purposes?		4.05	1.49
	Average Mean		3.56	

Analysis in Table 2 shows the mean and standard deviation of items on level of availability of instructional aids in senior secondary schools in Adamawa state, Nigeria. A high level of availability of instructional aids in senior secondary schools was obtained as indicated by the average mean of 3.56.

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Research Question 2

What is the level of availability of school facilities in senior secondary schools in Adamawa state?

Table 2: Mean and Standard Deviation of Level of Availability of School Facilities in Senior Secondary Schools in Adamawa State

S/N	ITEM	n = 221	Mean	S. D
11	How available are Classrooms rooms that accommodate students comfortably during classes		3.66	1.57
12	Are libraries available		4.07	1.50
13	How available are Library services		3.99	1.54
14	How available is portable water for drinking		3.73	1.62
15	How available is portable water for cleaning the school environment		3.39	1.67
16	How available are Staff rooms		3.57	1.54
17	How available are laboratories in the schools		3.73	1.43
18	How available are equipment in the Laboratories		3.64	1.43
19	How available are school gadgets in the Store room		3.60	1.46
20	How available are functional toilet system		4.37	1.00
Average Mean			3.77	

Result of analysis presented in Table 2 shows the mean and standard deviation of items on level of availability of school facilities in senior secondary schools in Adamawa state, Nigeria. The result shows that there is high level of availability of school facilities in senior secondary schools as indicated by the grand mean of 3.77.

Research Question 3

What is the level of adequacy of funding in senior secondary schools in Adamawa state?

Table 3: Mean and Standard Deviation of Level of Adequacy of Funding in Senior Secondary Schools in Adamawa State

S/N	ITEM	Mean	S. D
21	The allocation from the government is adequate	3.19	1.60
22	Internal generated funds from students school fees is a sufficient supplement	3.37	1.57
23	The fund from other educational organization is sufficient	3.54	1.54
24	The school source of fund increases per year	3.00	1.56
25	Parents P.T.A contribution has been a source of school funding.	3.17	1.55
26	Generally the secondary schools are well funded	3.32	1.48
Average Mean		3.27	

Analysis in Table 3 shows the mean and standard deviation of items on level of adequacy of funding in senior secondary schools in Adamawa state, Nigeria. An average mean of 3.27 indicates moderate level of adequacy of funding in senior secondary schools in Adamawa state, Nigeria.

Hypothesis Testing

H₀₁: There is no significant relationship between availability of instructional aids and Biology students’ academic achievement in senior secondary schools in Adamawa state.

Table 4: Summary of ANOVA of Linear Regression of Instructional Aids as Predictor of Biology Students’ Academic Achievement

Model		Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	18.278	1	18.278	14.368	.000 ^b
	Residual	278.609	219	1.272		

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Total	296.887	220
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- a. Dependent Variable: Students' academic performance
 b. Predictors: (Constant), instructional aids

Analysis in Table 4 shows that availability of instructional aids is a significant predictor of senior secondary school Biology students' academic achievement, $F_{(1, 220)} = 14.368$, $p < 0.05$. Since the p – value (0.000) is less than 0.05 alpha level, we can conclude that the null hypothesis should be rejected. This means that availability of instructional aids significantly predicts senior secondary school students' academic achievement.

Table 5: Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.248 ^a	.062	.057	1.12791

- a. Predictors: (Constant), INSTRUCTIONAL AIDS

The result in Table 5 shows a model summary which shows how the independent variable explains the variance in the dependent variable. The result shows that the availability of instructional aids explained 6.2% of the variance in students' academic Achievement.

Table 4c: Coefficients of Beta of Prediction between Instructional Aids and Students' Academic Performance

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Coefficients		
1	(Constant)	1.536	.400		3.843	.000
	INSTRUCTIONAL AIDS	.417	.110	.248	3.790	.000

- a. Dependent Variable: Students' academic performance

The result in Table 4c indicates the Beta coefficient of the regression analysis of availability of instructional aids and students' academic achievement. The result shows a beta coefficient of 0.234, $p < 0.05$. This indicates that availability of instructional aids is significantly related to students' academic performance.

H₀₂: There is no significant relationship between availability of school facilities and Biology students' academic achievement in senior secondary schools in Adamawa state.

Table 5a: Summary of ANOVA of Linear Regression of School Facilities as Predictor of Senior Secondary School Biology Students' Academic Achievement

Model		Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	20.281	1	20.281	16.057	.000 ^b
	Residual	276.606	219	1.263		
	Total	296.887	220			

- a. Dependent Variable: Students' academic performance
 b. Predictors: (Constant), school facilities

Results in Table 5a shows that there is significant relationship between availability of school facilities and senior secondary school students' academic performance, $F_{(1, 629)} = 16.057$, $p < 0.05$. Since the p – value (0.000) is less than 0.05 alpha level, we conclude that the null hypothesis is rejected. This means that availability of school facilities is significantly related to senior secondary school Biology students' academic performance.

Table 5b: Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.261 ^a	.068	.064	1.12385

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a. Predictors: (Constant), school facilities

The result in Table 5b shows a model summary which shows how the independent variable explains the variance in the dependent variable. The result shows that the school facilities explained 6.8% of the variance in students' academic achievement.

Table 5c: Coefficients of Beta of Prediction between School Facilities and Students' Academic Achievement

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients Beta	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error			
1	(Constant)	1.652	.350		4.713	.000
	SCHOOL FACILITIES	.363	.091	.261	4.007	.000

a. Dependent Variable: Students' academic performance

The result in Table 5c indicates the Beta coefficient of the regression analysis of school facilities and students' academic achievement. The result shows a beta coefficient of 0.316, $p < 0.05$. This indicates that school facilities is a significant predictor of academic performance.

H₀₃: There is no significant relationship between adequacy of funding and students' academic performance in senior secondary schools in Adamawa state.

Table 6a: Summary of ANOVA of Linear Regression of Relationship between Adequacy of Funding and Senior Secondary School Students' Academic Performance

Model		Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	31.664	1	31.664	26.145	.000 ^b
	Residual	265.223	219	1.211		
	Total	296.887	220			

a. Dependent Variable: Students' academic performance

b. Predictors: (Constant), adequacy of funds

Results of Analysis in Table 6a shows that there is significant relationship between adequacy of funding and senior secondary school students' academic performance, $F_{(1, 629)} = 26.145$, $p < 0.05$. Since the p – value (0.000) is less than 0.05 alpha level, we can conclude that the null hypothesis should be rejected. This means that adequacy of funding significantly predicts senior secondary school students' academic performance.

Table 6b: Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.327 ^a	.107	.103	1.10048

a. Predictors: (Constant), adequacy of funds

The result in Table 6b shows a model summary which shows how the independent variable explains the variance in the dependent variable. The result shows that adequacy of funding explained 2.8% of the variance in students' academic performance.

Table 6c: Coefficients of Beta of Prediction between Adequacy of Funds and Students' Academic Performance

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients Beta	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error			
1	(Constant)	1.650	.278		5.927	.000
	ADEQUACY OF FUNDS	.420	.082	.327	5.113	.000

a. Dependent Variable: Students' academic performance

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The result in Table 6c indicates the Beta coefficient of the regression analysis of adequacy of funding and students' academic achievement. The result shows a beta coefficient of 0.295, $p < 0.05$. This indicates that adequacy of funding is significantly related to students' academic performance.

Discussion of Findings

The study investigated the relationship between educational Resources and Biology students' academic performance in senior secondary schools in Adamawa state. The following are the discussion of findings of this study. The finding revealed that there is significant relationship between availability of instructional aids and senior secondary school Biology students' academic performance in Adamawa State. This is because instructional materials, in the teaching-learning process, facilitate the learning of abstract concepts and ideas; keep the learners busy and active thus, increasing their participation in the lesson; save teachers' energy of talking too much; illustrate the concepts clearer and better than the teachers' words only; help overcome the limitations of the classroom by making the inaccessible accessible; help to broaden students' knowledge, increase their level of understanding as well as discourage rote-learning; help to stimulate and motivate learners.

The finding also indicates that there is significant relationship between school facilities and senior secondary school Biology students' academic performance in Adamawa State. This means that availability of school facilities would enhance students' academic performance. The availability of material and resources in the school is as important as the presence of qualified personnel and when there is no qualified personnel and required material resources, there will be no effective teaching and learning and hence it would affect student's performances. The finding of the study agrees with that of Ekundayo (2018) who found that there was a significant relationship between school facilities and students' achievement in the affective and the psychomotor domains. This suggests that when the school facilities are better put in place and in use better performance are expected from the students. In similar studies by Ayodele (2000) and Vandiver (2011), a significant positive relationship is found between availability of facilities and student academic performance. This aspect is a key in determining the academic performance of learners in schools, thus the state of school facility and attendance directly impact on academic performance of learners and school in general.

Furthermore, the finding revealed that there is no significant relationship between adequacy of funding and senior secondary school Biology students' academic performance in Adamawa State. The level of funds available to a large extent determines the quantity and quality of school objectives that will be achieved. This is because funding is important in the acquisition of basic human, financial and material resources needed to transform the objectives of the school into reality. The finding of this study agrees with that of Nwite (2016) who found significant relationship between financial allocation and students' performance. Nwite reported that adequate financial resource allocations to secondary schools significantly influence students' performance. The finding is also in-line with the study of Abdul-Rahaman, Ming, Abdul-Rahaman, Amadu and Abdul-Rahaman (2018) who found that government funding in the form of progressive free senior high school policy has a significant effect on students' academic performance in Schools in the Wa Municipality of the Upper West Region of Ghana. The finding also concurs with that of Van der Berg (2017) who confirms an overwhelmingly positive impact of funding on student success. The finding however contradicted that of Kerkvliet and Nowell (2014) and Naidoo and McKay (2018) who found no relationship between the amount received and performance. The finding also is in concordance with that of Jane (2020) whose findings of the study indicate that government funding of secondary education improves school attendance, access and facilitate acquisition of teaching and learning facilities.

Conclusion

Based on the findings of this study, it is concluded that availability of educational resources (instructional aids, school facilities and adequacy of funding) enhanced senior secondary schools Biology students' academic performance in Adamawa state.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of the study, the following recommendations were made.

1. The government through the post primary school management board should make instructional aids available to schools to enable teachers teach effectively.
2. Adequate school facilities such as classrooms, laboratories, textbooks should be made available to provide an atmosphere and amenities for student success.

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3. Government should be committed to the adequate funding of secondary education through appropriate budgetary allocation for the sustenance of secondary education in the country. The government should consider an upward review of the educational budget to meet up with the 26% and above allocation recommended by UNESCO.

Acknowledgements

I would like to express my heartfelt gratitude to the principals, teachers, and students of senior secondary schools in Adamawa state for their invaluable contributions to this research. Your cooperation, willingness to participate, and the insights you shared have been instrumental in the successful completion of this study. Your dedication to education and your commitment to the pursuit of knowledge are truly commendable, and I am deeply appreciative of your support throughout this research endeavor. Thank you for your time, cooperation, and unwavering enthusiasm in advancing the understanding of educational challenges and opportunities in Adamawa state. Your involvement has enriched this study and will undoubtedly contribute to the improvement of education in the region.

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